

AUTOMAP Supplementary Material

This document contains proofs for the paper *AUTOMAP: Inferring Rank-Polymorphic Function Applications with Integer Linear Programming* [Schenck et al. 2024]. Each proposition is numbered and stated as it is in the paper and in the same corresponding sections.

4 Target Language

PROPOSITION 4.1 (TYPING CLOSED UNDER TYPE SUBSTITUTION). *If $\Gamma \vdash p : \sigma$ then $s_t(\Gamma) \vdash p : s_t(\sigma)$, for any type substitution s_t .*

PROOF. By induction over the typing derivation. The SV- rules for values are skipped because they're either trivial or analogous to the corresponding expression rules.

Case S-VAR ($\Gamma, x : \sigma \vdash x : \sigma$):

Immediate.

Case S-INST ($\Gamma \vdash e : \tau$):

We have [1] $\Gamma \vdash e : \sigma$ and [2] $\sigma \geq \tau$. By the IH, [3] $s_t(\Gamma) \vdash e : s_t(\sigma)$. Since \geq is closed under substitution, [1] yields [4] $s_t(\sigma) \geq s_t(\tau)$. Applying S-INST to [3] and [4] gives $s_t(\Gamma) \vdash e : s_t(\tau)$.

Case S-ARRAY ($\Gamma \vdash [e_1, \dots, e_n] : []\tau$):

We have [1] $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}. \Gamma \vdash e_i : \tau$. Applying the IH to [1], [2] $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}. s_t(\Gamma) \vdash e_i : s_t(\tau)$. Applying S-ARRAY to [2], $s_t(\Gamma) \vdash [v_1, \dots, v_n] : s_t([]\tau)$.

Case S-VAL ($\Gamma \vdash v : \tau$):

We have [1] $v : \tau$. Applying the IH to [1], [2] $v : s_t(\tau)$. Applying S-VAL to [2], $s_t(\Gamma) \vdash v : s_t(\tau)$.

Case S-FUN ($\Gamma \vdash \lambda x. e : \tau \rightarrow \tau'$):

We have [1] $\Gamma, x : \tau \vdash e : \tau'$. Applying the IH to [1], [2] $s_t(\Gamma), x : s_t(\tau) \vdash e : s_t(\tau')$. Applying S-FUN to [2], $s_t(\Gamma) \vdash \lambda x. e : s_t(\tau \rightarrow \tau')$.

Case S-APP ($\Gamma \vdash e_1 e_2 : \tau_2$):

We have [1] $\Gamma \vdash e_1 : \tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2$ and [2] $\Gamma \vdash e_2 : \tau_1$. Applying the IH to [1] and [2], we obtain [3] $s_t(\Gamma) \vdash e_1 : s_t(\tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2)$ and [4] $s_t(\Gamma) \vdash e_2 : s_t(\tau_1)$. Applying S-APP to [3] and [4], $s_t(\Gamma) \vdash e_1 e_2 : s_t(\tau_2)$.

Case S-MAP ($\Gamma \vdash \text{map } e_1 e_2 : []\tau_2$):

We have [1] $\Gamma \vdash e_1 : \tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2$ and [2] $\Gamma \vdash e_2 : []\tau_1$. Applying the IH to [1] and [2], we obtain [3] $s_t(\Gamma) \vdash e_1 : s_t(\tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2)$ and [4] $s_t(\Gamma) \vdash e_2 : s_t([]\tau_1)$. Applying S-MAP to [3] and [4], $s_t(\Gamma) \vdash \text{map } e_1 e_2 : s_t([]\tau_2)$.

Case S-REP ($\Gamma \vdash \text{rep } e : []\tau$):

We have [1] $\Gamma \vdash e : \tau$. Applying the IH to [1], [2] $s_t(\Gamma) \vdash e : s_t(\tau)$. Applying S-REP to [2], $s_t(\Gamma) \vdash \text{rep } e : s_t([]\tau)$.

Case S-DEF ($\Gamma \vdash \text{def } f x = e ; p : \sigma'$):

We have [1] $\Gamma, x : \tau \vdash e : \tau'$, [2] $\{\vec{\alpha}\} \cap \text{ftv}(\Gamma, \sigma') = \emptyset$, and [3] $\Gamma, f : \forall \vec{\alpha}. \tau \rightarrow \tau' \vdash p : \sigma'$. Choose $\{\vec{\alpha}'\}$ such that [4] $\{\vec{\alpha}'\} \cap \text{ftv}(s_t(\Gamma), s_t(\sigma), s_t) = \emptyset$ (where $\text{ftv}(s_t) = \{\text{ftv}(s_t(\beta)) \mid \beta \in \text{dom}(s_t)\}$) and there exists a bijective substitution s_{rename} between $\{\vec{\alpha}\}$ and $\{\vec{\alpha}'\}$. Since type schemes are equal up to bound variable renaming, we have [5] $\Gamma, f : \forall \vec{\alpha}'. s_{\text{rename}}(\tau \rightarrow \tau') \vdash p : \sigma'$. Applying the IH to [1] with the substitution $s_t \circ s_{\text{rename}}$ yields [6] $s_t(s_{\text{rename}}(\Gamma)), x : s_t(s_{\text{rename}}(\tau)) \vdash e : s_t(s_{\text{rename}}(\tau'))$. By [2] this is equivalent to [7] $s_t(\Gamma), x : s_t(s_{\text{rename}}(\tau)) \vdash e : s_t(s_{\text{rename}}(\tau'))$. Applying the IH to [5] with the substitution s_t

yields $s_t(\Gamma), f : \forall \vec{\alpha}'. s_t|_{V_t \setminus \{\vec{\alpha}'\}}(s_{\text{rename}}(\tau) \rightarrow s_{\text{rename}}(\tau')) \vdash p : s_t(\sigma')$ which is equivalent to $[8] s_t(\Gamma), f : \forall \vec{\alpha}'. s_t(s_{\text{rename}}(\tau)) \rightarrow s_t(s_{\text{rename}}(\tau')) \vdash p : s_t(\sigma')$ by [4]. Applying S-DEF to [7], [4], and [8] yields $s_t(\Gamma) \vdash \text{def } f x = e ; p : s_t(\sigma')$.

□

PROPOSITION 4.2 (UNIQUE DECOMPOSITION). *If $\vdash p : \sigma$ then either p is a value or there exists a type scheme σ' , a unique expression e , and a unique context K such that $p = K\langle e \rangle$ and $\vdash e : \sigma'$ and e is a redex.*

PROOF. By induction over the typing derivation.

Case S-VAR :

Impossible because an empty context is assumed.

Case S-INST ($\vdash e : \tau$):

We have [1] $\vdash e : \sigma$ and [2] $\sigma \geq \tau$. By the IH, there exists σ' and a unique redex e' and context K such that $e = K\langle e' \rangle$ and $\vdash e' : \sigma'$.

Case S-ARRAY ($\vdash [e_1, \dots, e_n] : []\tau$):

We have [1] $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}. \vdash e_i : \tau$. Applying the IH to [1], for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ either e_i is a value or there exists σ_i along with a unique redex e'_i and context K_i such that [2] $e_i = K_i\langle e'_i \rangle$ and $\vdash e'_i : \sigma_i$. If every e_i is a value, we're done. Otherwise, choose the i where e_i isn't a value and set $K = [e_1, \dots, e_{i-1}, C_i, e_{i+1}, \dots, e_n]$. By [2], $[e_1, \dots, e_n] = K\langle e'_i \rangle$ and K is unique by the uniqueness of K_i and the definition of contexts.

Case S-VAL ($\vdash v : \tau$):

v is a value.

Case S-FUN ($\vdash \lambda x. e : \tau \rightarrow \tau'$):

$\lambda x. e$ is a value.

Case S-APP ($\vdash e_1 e_2 : \tau_2$):

We have [1] $\vdash e_1 : \tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2$ and [2] $\vdash e_2 : \tau_1$.

Subcase e_1 isn't a value :

Applying the IH on [1], there exists σ'_1 and a unique redex e'_1 and context K_1 such that [3] $e_1 = K_1\langle e'_1 \rangle$ and [4] $\vdash e'_1 : \sigma'_1$. Choosing $K = K_1 e_2$, we have $e_1 e_2 = K\langle e'_1 \rangle$ as required.

Subcase e_1 is a value and e_2 isn't a value :

Analogous to the previous case, except $K = e_1 K_2$ where K_2 is the context obtained by invoking the IH on [2].

Subcase e_1 is a value and e_2 is a value :

Since $e_1 e_2$ is a redex, we simply choose $K = \langle \cdot \rangle$.

Case S-MAP ($\vdash \text{map } e_1 e_2 : []\tau_2$):

The proof for this case proceed nearly identically to the one for S-APP (except a map-context is chosen except for an application context).

Case S-REP ($\vdash \text{rep } e : []\tau$):

We have [1] $\vdash e : \tau$. If e is a value, we're done. Otherwise, applying the IH to [1], there exists σ' and a unique redex e' and context K' such that [2] $e = K'\langle e' \rangle$ and $\vdash e' : \sigma'$. By [2], choosing $K = \text{rep } C'$ we have $e = K\langle e' \rangle$.

Case S-DEF ($\vdash \text{def } f x = e ; p : \sigma'$):

This case is a redex, so we simply choose $K = \langle \cdot \rangle$.

□

PROPOSITION 4.3 (TYPING CLOSED UNDER VALUE SUBSTITUTION). *If $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash p : \sigma$ and $\vdash v : \sigma'$ then $\Gamma \vdash p[v/x] : \sigma$.*

PROOF. By induction over $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash p : \sigma$. The SV- rules for values are skipped because they're either trivial or analogous to the corresponding expression rules.

Case S-VAR ($\Gamma, y : \sigma \vdash y : \sigma$):

If $x \neq y$ then $\Gamma, y : \sigma \vdash y[v/x] : \sigma$ is equivalent to $\Gamma, y : \sigma \vdash y : \sigma$, which clearly holds by S-VAR. If $x = y$, then $\Gamma, y : \sigma \vdash y[v/x] : \sigma$ is equivalent to $\Gamma, x : \sigma \vdash v : \sigma$, which holds by assumption.

Case S-INST ($\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash e : \tau$):

We have [1] $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash e : \sigma$ and [2] $\sigma \geq \tau$. By the IH, [3] $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash e[v/x] : \sigma$ and applying S-INST to [2] and [3] yields $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash e[v/x] : \tau$.

Case S-ARRAY ($\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash [e_1, \dots, e_n] : []\tau$):

We have [1] $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}. \Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash e_i : \tau$. Applying the IH to [1], [2] $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}. \Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash e_i[v/x] : \tau$. Applying S-ARRAY to [2], $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash [e_1[v/x], \dots, e_n[v/x]] : []\tau$.

Case S-VAL ($\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash v' : \tau$):

$\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash v' : \tau$ is equal to $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash v'[v/x] : \tau$ because values cannot contain free variables.

Case S-FUN ($\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash \lambda y. e : \tau \rightarrow \tau'$):

If $y = x$, then $(\lambda y. e)[v/x]$ is equivalent to $\lambda y. e$ and we're done. Otherwise, assume $y \neq x$. We have [1] which is equivalent to [2] $\Gamma, y : \tau, x : \sigma' \vdash e : \tau'$ (since $y \neq x$). Applying the IH to [2], [3] $\Gamma, y : \tau, x : \sigma' \vdash e[v/x] : \tau'$, which is equivalent to [4] $\Gamma, x : \sigma', y : \tau \vdash e[v/x] : \tau'$. Applying S-FUN to [4], $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash \lambda y. (e[v/x]) : \tau \rightarrow \tau'$, which is equivalent to $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash (\lambda y. e)[v/x] : \tau \rightarrow \tau'$.

Case S-APP ($\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash e_1 e_2 : \tau_2$):

We have [1] $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash e_1 : \tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2$ and [2] $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash e_2 : \tau_1$. Applying the IH to [1] and [2], we obtain [3] $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash e_1[v/x] : \tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2$ and [4] $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash e_2[v/x] : \tau_1$. Applying S-APP to [3] and [4], $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash (e_1 e_2)[v/x] : \tau_2$.

Case S-MAP ($\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash \text{map } e_1 e_2 : []\tau_2$):

We have [1] $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash e_1 : \tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2$ and [2] $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash e_2 : []\tau_1$. Applying the IH to [1] and [2], we obtain [3] $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash e_1[v/x] : \tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2$ and [4] $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash e_2[v/x] : []\tau_1$. Applying S-MAP to [3] and [4], $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash (\text{map } e_1 e_2)[v/x] : []\tau_2$.

Case S-REP ($\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash \text{rep } e : []\tau$):

We have [1] $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash e : \tau$. Applying the IH to [1], [2] $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash e[v/x] : \tau$. Applying S-REP to [2], $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash (\text{rep } e)[v/x] : []\tau$.

Case S-DEF ($\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash \text{def } f y = e ; p : \sigma'$):

We have [1] $\Gamma, y : \tau \vdash e : \tau'$, [2] $\{\vec{\alpha}\} \cap \text{ftv}(\Gamma, \sigma') = \emptyset$, and [3] $\Gamma, f : \forall \vec{\alpha}. \tau \rightarrow \tau' \vdash p : \sigma'$. If $x = y$, $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash (\text{def } f y = e ; p)[v/x] : \sigma'$ is equivalent to $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash \text{def } f y = e ; p[v/x] : \sigma'$ which holds by applying the IH to [2] to obtain [4] $\Gamma, x : \sigma', f : \forall \vec{\alpha}. \tau \rightarrow \tau' \vdash p[v/x] : \sigma'$ and then applying S-DEF to [1], [2], and [4]. If $x \neq y$, then applying the IH to [2] yields [5] $\Gamma, y : \tau, x : \sigma' \vdash e[v/x] : \tau'$, from which $\Gamma, x : \sigma' \vdash (\text{def } f y = e ; p)[v/x] : \sigma'$ follows by applying S-DEF to [5], [2], and [4].

□

PROPOSITION 4.4 (PROGRESS). *If $\vdash p : \sigma$ then either p is a value or there exists p' such that $p \rightsquigarrow p'$.*

PROOF. If p isn't a value, by proposition 4.2 there exists a unique e' and K such that $e = K\langle e' \rangle$, $\vdash e' : \sigma'$, and e' is a redex. Because e' is a redex, there exists e'' such that $e' \rightsquigarrow e''$. Hence, $e = K\langle e' \rangle \rightsquigarrow K\langle e'' \rangle$. □

PROPOSITION 4.5 (PRESERVATION). *If $\vdash p : \sigma$ and $p \rightsquigarrow p'$ then $\vdash p' : \sigma$.*

PROOF. By induction over the typing derivation.

Case S-VAR :

Impossible because an empty context is assumed.

Case S-INST ($\vdash e : \tau$):

We have [1] $\vdash e : \sigma$, [2] $\sigma \geq \tau$, and [4] $e \rightsquigarrow e'$. Applying the IH, to [1] and [4] yields [5] $\vdash e' : \sigma$. Applying S-INST to [5] and [2] yields $\vdash e' : \tau$

Case S-ARRAY ($\vdash [e_1, \dots, e_n] : []\tau$):

We have [1] $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}. \vdash e_i : \tau$ By proposition 4.2, there is a σ_i , a unique context K , and unique expressions e, e' such that that [3] $[e_1, \dots, e_n] = K\langle e \rangle$, [4] $\vdash e : \sigma'$, [5] $e \rightsquigarrow e'$, and [6] $K\langle e \rangle \rightsquigarrow K\langle e' \rangle$. From the reduction rules, we have [7] $K = [e_1, \dots, e_{i-1}, K', e_{i+1}, \dots, e_n]$ where [8] $e_i = K'\langle e \rangle$. By [6] and [7], [9] $K'\langle e \rangle \rightsquigarrow K'\langle e' \rangle$. Applying the IH using [1] and [9], we have [10] $\vdash K'\langle e' \rangle : \sigma_i$. By [3], [10], and [7] we have $\vdash K\langle e' \rangle : []\tau$.

Case S-VAL ($\vdash v : \tau$):

v is a value, so no reduction is possible.

Case S-FUN ($\vdash \lambda x. e : \tau \rightarrow \tau'$):

$\lambda x. e$ is a function, so no reduction is possible.

Case S-APP ($\vdash e_1 e_2 : \tau_2$):

We have [1] $\vdash e_1 : \tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2$ and [2] $\vdash e_2 : \tau_1$.

Subcase e_1 isn't a value :

By proposition 4.2, there is a σ , a unique context K , and unique expressions e, e' such that that [3] $e_1 e_2 = K\langle e \rangle$, [4] $\vdash e : \sigma'$, [5] $e \rightsquigarrow e'$, and [6] $K\langle e \rangle \rightsquigarrow K\langle e' \rangle$. Since e_1 isn't a value, by the uniqueness of K , there exists unique K' such that [7] $K = K' e_2$, [8] $e_1 = K'\langle e \rangle$, and [9] $K'\langle e \rangle \rightsquigarrow K'\langle e' \rangle$. Applying the IH to [1] and [9] yields [10] $\vdash K'\langle e' \rangle : \tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2$. Applying S-APP to [9] and [2] yields $\vdash K\langle e' \rangle : \tau_2$.

Subcase e_1 is a value and e_2 isn't :

Analogous to the previous case with $K = e_1 K'$.

Subcase e_1 and e_2 are values :

In this case, $e_1 e_2$ is a redex and the property follows by proposition 4.3.

Case S-MAP ($\Gamma \vdash \text{map } e_1 e_2 : []\tau_2$):

Analogous to S-APP except with a map context.

Case S-REP ($\Gamma \vdash \text{rep } e : []\tau$):

We have [1] $\Gamma \vdash e : \tau$. If e is a value, there's nothing to show, so assume e isn't a value.

The proof proceeds similarly to the other cases, just with the context $K = \text{rep}K'$.

Case S-DEF ($\Gamma \vdash \text{def } f x = e ; p : \sigma'$):

A def is always a redex and the property follows by proposition 4.3.

□

6 Rank Analysis

6.5 Constraint Set Solving

In this section, we prove proposition 6.1 and proposition 6.2 from the paper. To prove the propositions, we introduce the notion of a *closed rank*. The *closed rank* of a closed shape or closed type, written $|\cdot|^\circ$, denotes the non-negative integral rank of a closed shape (S°) or a closed type (τ°). It

is defined as

$$\begin{array}{ll} |[] |^\circ = 1 & |S \tau|^\circ = |S|^\circ + |\tau|^\circ \\ |S_1 S_2|^\circ = |S_1|^\circ + |S_2|^\circ & |\alpha|^\circ = 0 \\ | \bullet |^\circ = 0 & |\tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2|^\circ = 0 \\ |\text{int}|^\circ = 0 & \end{array}$$

LEMMA 6.1. *Given a closed substitution s and rank substitution s_r , if $s_r(Q) = s(Q)$ and $s_r(\bar{\alpha}) = |s(\alpha)|^\circ$ then $|s(S)|^\circ = s_r(|S|)$ and $|s(\tau)|^\circ = s_r(|\tau|)$.*

PROOF. The first statement, $[1] |s(S)|^\circ = s_r(|S|)$, follows by induction over S .

Case closed shapes (S°):

Immediate, since $|s(S^\circ)|^\circ = |S^\circ| = s_r(|S^\circ|)$.

Case rank power ($[]^\circ$):

We have $|s([]^\circ)|^\circ = s(Q) = s_r(Q) = s_r(|[]^\circ|)$.

Case concatenation ($S_1 S_2$):

We have $|s(S_1 S_2)|^\circ = |s(S_1)|^\circ + |s(S_2)|^\circ = s_r(|S_1|) + s_r(|S_2|) = s_r(|S_1 S_2|)$ by the IH.

The second statement, $|s(\tau)|^\circ = s_r(|\tau|)$, follows by induction over τ , using the first statement.

Case function type ($\tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2$):

We have $|s(\tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2)|^\circ = |s(\tau_1) \rightarrow s(\tau_2)|^\circ = 0 = s_r(0) = s_r(|\tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2|)$

Case array type ($S' \tau'$):

By [1], we have [2] $|s(S')|^\circ = s_r(|S'|)$. By the IH, we have [3] $|s(\tau')|^\circ = s_r(|\tau'|)$. Combining [2] and [3] gives $|s(S' \tau')|^\circ = |s(S')|^\circ + |s(\tau')|^\circ = s_r(|S'|) + s_r(|\tau'|) = s_r(|S' \tau'|)$.

Case integer (int):

Trivial.

Case closed function type ($\tau_1^\circ \rightarrow \tau_2^\circ$):

Analogous to the function type case.

Case closed array type ($S^{\circ'} \tau^{\circ'}$):

Analogous to the array type case.

Case type variable (α):

We have $|s(\alpha)|^\circ = s_r(\bar{\alpha}) = s_r(|\alpha|)$.

□

LEMMA 6.2. *If s satisfies C then the rank substitution s_r defined by $s_r(Q) = s(Q)$ and $s_r(\bar{\alpha}) = |s(\alpha)|^\circ$ satisfies $|C|$.*

PROOF. Case analysis on the constraints of C . Since s satisfies C , note that $s|_{\text{ftv}(C)}$ must be closed.

Case $M \vee R$:

Immediate by the definition of s_r .

Case $\tau_1 \doteq \tau_2$:

By lemma 6.1, $|s(S)|^\circ = s_r(|S|)$ and $|s(\tau)|^\circ = s_r(|\tau|)$. Hence, $s_r(|\tau_1|) = |s(\tau_1)|^\circ = |s(\tau_2)|^\circ = s_r(|\tau_2|)$, as required.

□

PROPOSITION 6.1. *If s satisfies C , there exists a rank substitution s_r that satisfies $|C|$ and there exists a closed type substitution s_t such that $s|_{\text{ftv}(C) \cup \text{frv}(C)} = s_t \circ s_r$.*

PROOF. By lemma 6.2, the rank substitution s_r defined by $s_r(Q) = s(Q)$ and $s_r(\bar{\alpha}) = |s(\alpha)|^\circ$ satisfies $|C|$. Define $s_t = s|_{\text{ftv}(C)}$. Since s satisfies C , s_t must be closed (i.e., s_t does not map any type variables to types with rank variables). Now, $(s_t \circ s_r)(Q) = s_r(Q) = s(Q)$. Additionally, $(s_t \circ s_r)(\alpha) = s_t(\alpha) = s|_{\text{ftv}(C)}(\alpha)$ for each $\alpha \in \text{ftv}(C)$. □

LEMMA 6.2. Consider a constraint set C and suppose s satisfies C and s_r satisfies $|C|$. Define

$$\begin{aligned} s'(Q) &= s_r(Q) & \text{basetype}(S\tau) &= \text{basetype}(\tau) \\ s'(\alpha) &= \llbracket \rrbracket^{s_r(\bar{\alpha})} \text{basetype}(s(\alpha)), & \text{basetype}(\tau) &= \tau. \end{aligned}$$

Then s' satisfies C .

PROOF. By case analysis over the constraints of C .

Case $M \vee R$:

Immediate by the definition of s' .

Case $\tau_1 \doteq \tau_2$:

We need to show that $\llbracket 1 \rrbracket \text{basetype}(s'(\tau_1)) = \text{basetype}(s'(\tau_2))$ and $\llbracket 2 \rrbracket |s'(\tau_1)|^\circ = |s'(\tau_2)|^\circ$, since this implies $s'(\tau_1) = s'(\tau_2)$. $\llbracket 1 \rrbracket$ is immediate by the definition of s' and basetype . Note that s' must be closed over C because s_r satisfies $|C|_r$ and s satisfies C . We have $\llbracket 3 \rrbracket s_r(Q) = s'(Q)$ and $\llbracket 4 \rrbracket s_r(\bar{\alpha}) = \llbracket \rrbracket^{s_r(\bar{\alpha})} \text{basetype}(s(\alpha))|^\circ = |s'(\alpha)|^\circ$. Applying $\llbracket 3 \rrbracket$ and $\llbracket 4 \rrbracket$ to lemma 6.1 yields $s_r(|\tau|) = |s'(\tau)|^\circ$ for any τ , and hence $\llbracket 2 \rrbracket$ reduces to $s_r(|\tau_1|) = s_r(|\tau_2|)$, which follows by the fact that s_r satisfies $|C|$. \square

PROPOSITION 6.2. If C is satisfiable and s_r satisfies $|C|$ then there is a closed type substitution s_t such that the substitution $s = s_t \circ s_r$ satisfies C .

PROOF. Using the construction from lemma 6.2, there is a satisfier s' of C with $s'(Q) = s_r(Q)$ and $|s'(\alpha)|^\circ = s_r(\bar{\alpha})$. Because s' satisfies C , $s'|_{\text{ftv}(C)}$ is closed. Defining $s_t = s'|_{\text{ftv}(C)}$, we have $s(\alpha) = (s_t \circ s_r)(\alpha) = s_t(\alpha) = s'(\alpha)$ for each $\alpha \in \text{ftv}(C)$ and hence $s = s_t \circ s_r$ satisfies C . \square

7 Transformation to the target language

7.1 Well-Typedness

LEMMA 7.1. If $\sigma \geq \tau$ then $S\sigma \geq S\tau$.

PROOF. Let $\sigma = \forall \bar{\alpha}. \tau'$. By definition, there exists a type substitution s_t such that $\text{dom}(s_t) = \{\bar{\alpha}\}$ and $s_t(\tau') = \tau$. But then $Ss_t(\tau') = S\tau$ and hence $s_t(S\tau') = S\tau$ because s_t has no affect on shapes. \square

PROPOSITION 7.1 (WELL-TYPEDNESS FOR EXPRESSIONS). If $\Gamma \vdash e :_S \sigma \parallel C$ and s is a satisfier of C , then $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(e)) : s(S\sigma)$

PROOF. By induction over the typing derivation.

Case C-INT ($\vdash n : \text{int} \parallel \emptyset$):

Immediate by the definition of AM.

Case C-INST ($\Gamma \vdash e : \tau \parallel \emptyset$):

We have $\llbracket 1 \rrbracket \Gamma \vdash e : \sigma \parallel \emptyset$ and $\llbracket 2 \rrbracket \sigma \geq \tau$. By the IH, $\llbracket 3 \rrbracket s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(e)) : s(S\sigma)$. Applying ?? to $\llbracket 2 \rrbracket$ yields $\llbracket 4 \rrbracket s(\sigma) \geq s(\tau)$. By lemma 7.1 and $\llbracket 4 \rrbracket$, $\llbracket 5 \rrbracket s(S\sigma) \geq s(S\tau)$. Applying S-INST to $\llbracket 3 \rrbracket$ and $\llbracket 5 \rrbracket$ yields $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(e)) : s(S\tau)$ as required.

Case C-VAR ($\Gamma, x : \sigma \vdash x : \sigma \parallel \emptyset$):

Immediate by the definition of AM.

Case C-ARRAY ($\Gamma \vdash [e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n] : \llbracket \rrbracket S_1\tau_1 \parallel \{S_1\tau_1 \doteq S_k\tau_k \mid k \in \{2, \dots, n\}\} \cup C_1 \cup \dots \cup C_n$):

We have $\llbracket 1 \rrbracket \forall k \in \{1, \dots, n\}. \Gamma \vdash e_k :_{S_k} \tau_k \parallel C_k$. Applying the IH to $\llbracket 1 \rrbracket$ yields $\llbracket 2 \rrbracket \forall k \in \{1, \dots, n\}. s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(e_k)) : s(S_k\tau_k)$. Since s satisfies C , $s(S_k\tau_k) = s(S_1\tau_1)$ for all $k \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ and hence $\llbracket 3 \rrbracket \forall k \in \{1, \dots, n\}. s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(e_k)) : s(S_1\tau_1)$. Applying S-ARRAY to $\llbracket 3 \rrbracket$ yields $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}([e_1, \dots, e_n]) : s(\llbracket \rrbracket S_1\tau_1)$.

Case C-APP ($\Gamma \vdash e_1 e_2 \Delta (M, R) ; \llbracket \rrbracket_{S_1}^M \tau_2 \parallel C \cup C_1 \cup C_2$):

We have [1] $\Gamma \vdash e_1 ;_{S_1} \tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2 \parallel C_1$, [2] $\Gamma \vdash e_2 ;_{S_2} \tau_3 \parallel C_2$, and [3] $C = \{M \vee R, \llbracket \rrbracket_{S_1}^M S_1 \tau_1 \doteq \llbracket \rrbracket_{S_2}^R S_2 \tau_3\}$. Applying the IH to [1] and [2], we have [4] $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(e_1)) : s(S_1 \tau_1) \rightarrow s(S_1 \tau_2)$ and [5] $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(e_2)) : s(S_2 \tau_3)$. Since s satisfies C , we also have [6] $s(M) = 0$ or $s(R) = 0$ and [7] $s(\llbracket \rrbracket_{S_1}^M S_1 \tau_1) = s(\llbracket \rrbracket_{S_2}^R S_2 \tau_3)$. We now case on [6].

Subcase $s(R) = 0$:

By [7], we have [8] $s(\llbracket \rrbracket_{S_1}^M S_1 \tau_1) = s(S_2 \tau_3)$. By [5] and [8] we have [9] $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(e_2)) : s(\llbracket \rrbracket_{S_1}^M S_1 \tau_1)$. Starting with [4] and [9] and applying the **S-MAP** rule M times, we have $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{map}^S(M) \text{AM}(s(e_1)) \text{AM}(s(e_2)) : s(\llbracket \rrbracket_{S_1}^M S_1 \tau_2)$ which, by the definition of AM , is the same as $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(e_1 e_2 \Delta (M, R))) : s(\llbracket \rrbracket_{S_1}^M S_1 \tau_2)$.

Subcase $s(M) = 0$:

By [7], we have [8] $s(S_1 \tau_1) = s(\llbracket \rrbracket_{S_2}^R S_2 \tau_3)$. By [4] and [8] we have [9] $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(e_1)) : s(\llbracket \rrbracket_{S_2}^R S_2 \tau_3) \rightarrow s(S_1 \tau_2)$. Starting with [5] and applying the **S-REP** rule R times, we have [10] $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{rep}^R \text{AM}(s(e_2)) : s(\llbracket \rrbracket_{S_2}^R S_2 \tau_3)$. Applying **S-APP** to [9] and [10] yields $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(e_1)) (\text{rep}^R \text{AM}(s(e_2))) : s(S_1 \tau_2)$ which is the same as $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(e_1 e_2 \Delta (M, R))) : s(S_1 \tau_2)$ by the definition of AM .

Case C-FUN ($\Gamma \vdash \lambda x. e : \tau_1 \rightarrow S \tau_2 \parallel C$):

We have [1] $\Gamma, x : \tau_1 \vdash e ;_S \tau_2 \parallel C$. Applying the IH to [1], [2] $s(\Gamma, x : \tau_1) \vdash \text{AM}(s(e)) : s(S \tau_2)$ Applying **S-FUN** to [2], $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(\lambda x. e)) : s(\tau_1) \rightarrow s(S \tau_2)$

Case C-MAP ($\Gamma \vdash \text{map } e_1 e_2 ; \llbracket \rrbracket_{S_1} \tau_2 \parallel \{\llbracket \rrbracket_{S_1} S_1 \tau_1 \doteq S_2 \tau_3\} \cup C_1 \cup C_2$):

We have [1] $\Gamma \vdash e_1 ;_{S_1} \tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2 \parallel C_1$ and [2] $\Gamma \vdash e_2 ;_{S_2} \tau_3 \parallel C_2$. Applying the IH to [1] and [2], we have [3] $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(e_1)) : s(S_1 \tau_1) \rightarrow s(S_1 \tau_2)$ and [4] $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(e_2)) : s(S_2 \tau_3)$. Since $s(\llbracket \rrbracket_{S_1} S_1 \tau_1) = s(S_2 \tau_3)$, by [4] we have [5] $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(e_2)) : s(\llbracket \rrbracket_{S_1} S_1 \tau_1)$. Applying **S-MAP** to [3] and [5], $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{map } \text{AM}(s(e_1)) \text{AM}(s(e_2)) : \llbracket \rrbracket_{S_1} S_1 \tau_2$, which is the same as $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(\text{map } e_1 e_2)) : s(\llbracket \rrbracket_{S_1} S_1 \tau_2)$.

Case C-REP ($\Gamma \vdash \text{rep } e : \llbracket \rrbracket S \tau \parallel C$):

We have [1] $\Gamma \vdash e ;_S \tau \parallel C$. Applying the IH to [1], we have [2] $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(e)) : s(S \tau)$. Applying **S-REP** to [2], we have $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{rep } \text{AM}(s(e)) : \llbracket \rrbracket s(S \tau)$, which is the same as $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{AM}(s(\text{rep } e)) : s(\llbracket \rrbracket S \tau)$.

□

PROPOSITION 7.2 (WELL-TYPEDNESS). *If $\Gamma \vdash p : \sigma$ then $\Gamma \vdash \text{AM}(p) : \sigma$.*

PROOF. By induction on $\Gamma \vdash p : \sigma$.

Case C-DEF ($\Gamma \vdash \text{def } f x = s(e) ; p : \sigma'$):

We have [1] $\Gamma, x : \tau \vdash e : \tau' \parallel C$, [2] s satisfies C , [3] $\{\vec{\alpha}\} \cap \text{ftv}(s(\Gamma), \sigma') = \emptyset$, [4] $s(\Gamma), f : \forall \vec{\alpha}. s(\tau) \rightarrow s(\tau') \vdash p : \sigma'$. Applying the IH on [4] yields [5] $s(\Gamma), f : \forall \vec{\alpha}. s(\tau) \rightarrow s(\tau') \vdash \text{AM}(p) : \sigma'$ and applying proposition 7.1 on [1] using [2] yields [6] $s(\Gamma, x : \tau) \vdash \text{AM}(s(e)) : s(\tau')$. Applying **S-DEF** to [6], [3], and [5] yields $s(\Gamma) \vdash \text{def } f x = \text{AM}(s(e)) ; \text{AM}(p) : \sigma'$.

□

7.2 Backwards Consistency

LEMMA 7.3. *If $\Gamma \vdash \mathcal{K}(e) ;_S \sigma \parallel C$ then there exists σ', S' , and C' such that $\Gamma \vdash e ;_{S'} \sigma' \parallel C'$.*

PROOF. By induction on \mathcal{K} . We only show a couple of cases; the remaining cases are analogous and follow by the IH.

Case $\mathcal{K} = \langle \cdot \rangle$:

Immediate.

Case $\mathcal{K} = \mathcal{K}' e_2 \Delta (M, R)$:

We have [1] $\Gamma \vdash \mathcal{K}' \langle e \rangle e_2 \Delta (M, R) :_S \sigma \parallel C$. By inversion of **C-APP**, there exists τ_1, τ_2, C_1 , and S_1 such that [2] $\Gamma \vdash \mathcal{K}' \langle e \rangle :_{S_1} \tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2 \parallel C_1$. Applying the IH to [2] yields the required result. \square

PROPOSITION 7.3 (REMOVAL WELL-TYPEDNESS). *If $\mathcal{K} \langle e \rangle \prec_{rem} \mathcal{K}' \langle e' \rangle$ and $\Gamma \vdash \mathcal{K} \langle e \rangle :_S \sigma \parallel C$ then there exists S', σ' , and C' such that*

- (a) $\Gamma \vdash \mathcal{K}' \langle e' \rangle :_{S'} \sigma' \parallel C'$.
- (b) If s_r satisfies $|C|$, then there exists \hat{s}'_r such that $s_r \circ \hat{s}'_r$ satisfies $|C'|$.
- (c) $C \simeq \hat{s}'_r(C')$.

PROOF. By inversion on the removal relation, we have [1] M, R fresh. We proceed by induction on \mathcal{K} .

Case $\mathcal{K} = \langle \cdot \rangle$:

We proceed by cases on the removal relation.

Subcase REM-MAP ($\text{map } e_1 e_2 \prec_{rem} e_1 e_2 \Delta (M, R)$):

We have [2] $\text{map } e_1 e_2 \prec_{rem} e_1 e_2 \Delta (M, R)$ and [3] $\Gamma \vdash \text{map } e_1 e_2 :_S \sigma \parallel C$. By inversion of [3], there exists $\tau_1, \tau_2, C_1, C_2, S_2$ such that [4] $\Gamma \vdash e_1 :_S \tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2 \parallel C_1$, [5] $\Gamma \vdash e_2 :_{S_2} \tau_3 \parallel C_2$, [6] $C = \{[\] S \tau_1 \doteq S_2 \tau_3\} \cup C_1 \cup C_2$, and [7] $\tau_2 = \sigma$. Define [8] $C'' = \{M \vee R, [\]^M S \tau_1 \doteq [\]^R S_2 \tau_2\}$.

- (a) Applying **C-APP** to [1], [4], [5], and [8] yields [9] $\Gamma \vdash e_1 e_2 \Delta (M, R) :_{[\]^M S} \tau_2 \parallel C'' \cup C_1 \cup C_2$, which is the same as $\Gamma \vdash \mathcal{K}' \langle e' \rangle :_{S'} \sigma' \parallel C'$ with $e' = e_1 e_2 \Delta (M, R)$, $S' = [\]^M S$, $\sigma' = \tau_2$, and $C' = C'' \cup C_1 \cup C_2$.
- (b) Suppose s_r satisfies $|C|$. The only difference between C and C' is that C contains $\{[\] S \tau_1 \doteq S_2 \tau_3\}$ whereas C' contains $\{M \vee R, [\]^M S \tau_1 \doteq [\]^R S_2 \tau_2\}$. Define $\hat{s}'_r = [M \mapsto 1, R \mapsto 0]$. Then, [10] $\hat{s}'_r(\{|M \vee R, [\]^M S \tau_1 \doteq [\]^R S_2 \tau_2\}) = \{1 \vee 0, [\] S \tau_1 \doteq S_2 \tau_2\}$, which is clearly satisfied by s_r .
- (c) By [10], the only difference between C and $\hat{s}'_r(C')$ is that the latter contains the additional variable-free constraint $1 \vee 0$, which is trivially satisfied by any substitution.

Subcase REM-REP ($\text{rep } e \prec_{rem} (\lambda x. x) e \Delta (M, R)$):

We have [2] $\text{rep } e \prec_{rem} (\lambda x. x) e \Delta (M, R)$ and [3] $\Gamma \vdash \text{rep } e : \sigma \parallel C$. By inversion of [3], there exists τ and S_1 with $\sigma = [\] S_1 \tau$ such that [4] $\Gamma \vdash e :_{S_1} \tau \parallel C$. By **C-FUN**, we have [5] $\Gamma \vdash \lambda x. x : \alpha \rightarrow \alpha \parallel \emptyset$, where α can be chosen fresh. Define [6] $C'' = \{M \vee R, [\]^M \alpha \doteq [\]^R S_1 \tau\}$.

- (a) Applying **C-APP** to [1], [4], [5], and [6] yields [9] $\Gamma \vdash \text{id } e \Delta (M, R) :_{[\]^M} \alpha \parallel C'' \cup C$, as required.
- (b) Suppose s_r satisfies $|C|$. The only difference between C and C' is that C' additionally contains the constraints of [6] (i.e., $\{M \vee R, [\]^M \alpha \doteq [\]^R S_1 \tau\}$). Define $\hat{s}'_r = [M \mapsto 0, R \mapsto 1, \bar{\alpha} \mapsto [\] S_1 \tau]$. Then, [10] $\hat{s}'_r(\{|M \vee R, [\]^M \alpha \doteq [\]^R S_1 \tau\}) = \{0 \vee 1, \bar{\alpha} \doteq [\] S_1 \tau\}$, which is obviously satisfied by s_r .
- (c) Since α can always be chosen uniquely fresh, we assume that it only appears in the constraint $\alpha \doteq [\] S_1 \tau$ (and hence can be trivially satisfied by the mapping $\alpha \mapsto [\] S_1 \tau$). Since both constraints of [10] are always satisfiable, we conclude that C and $\hat{s}'_r(C')$ are equivalent.

Case $\mathcal{K} = \text{rep } \mathcal{K}'$:

We have [2] $\text{rep } \mathcal{K}' \langle e \rangle \prec_{rem} \text{rep } \mathcal{K}' \langle e' \rangle$ and [3] $\Gamma \vdash \text{rep } \mathcal{K}' \langle e \rangle :_S \sigma \parallel C$. [2] implies

[4] $\mathcal{K}'\langle e \rangle \prec_{\text{rem}} \mathcal{K}'\langle e' \rangle$ by the definition of the removal relation. By lemma 7.3, there exists S', σ' , and C' such that [5] $\Gamma \vdash e :_{S'} \sigma' \parallel C'$.

- (a) Applying the IH to [4] and [5], there exists S'', σ'' , and C'' such that [5] $\Gamma \vdash \mathcal{K}'\langle e' \rangle :_{S''} \sigma'' \parallel C''$. Applying C-REP to [5] yields $\Gamma \vdash \text{rep } \mathcal{K}'\langle e' \rangle : [] S'' \sigma'' \parallel C''$.
- (b) Suppose s_r satisfies $|C|$. Applying the IH to [5] says that there exists s'_r such that $s_r \circ \hat{s}'_r$ satisfies $|C''|$.
- (c) Immediate by the inductive hypothesis since the rep constructor does not augment the constraint set.

The remaining context cases are analogous to the $\mathcal{K} = \text{rep } \mathcal{K}'$ case and are proved by invoking the inductive hypothesis. \square

PROPOSITION 7.4 (BACKWARDS CONSISTENCY). *If $\mathcal{K}\langle e \rangle \prec_{\text{rem}} \mathcal{K}\langle e' \rangle$, $\Gamma \vdash \mathcal{K}\langle e \rangle :_S \sigma \parallel C$, and s_r is unambiguous at size k for $|C|$, then there exists S', σ', C', s'_r such that $\Gamma \vdash \mathcal{K}\langle e' \rangle :_{S'} \sigma' \parallel C'$ and, if s'_r is unambiguous at size $k + 1$ for $|C'|$, then $\text{AM}(s_r(\mathcal{K}\langle e \rangle)) = \text{AM}(s'_r(\mathcal{K}\langle e' \rangle))$.*

PROOF. By proposition 7.3, there exists by S', σ', C', s'_r such that $\Gamma \vdash \mathcal{K}\langle e' \rangle :_{S'} \sigma' \parallel C'$. We proceed by induction on \mathcal{K} .

Case $\mathcal{K} = \langle \cdot \rangle$:

We proceed by cases on the removal relation.

Subcase REM-MAP ($\text{map } e_1 e_2 \prec_{\text{rem}} e_1 e_2 \Delta (M, R)$):

By the definition of AM, we have [1] $\text{AM}(s_r(\mathcal{K}\langle e \rangle)) = \text{AM}(s_r(\text{map } e_1 e_2)) = \text{map } \text{AM}(s_r(e_1)) \text{AM}(s_r(e_2))$ and [2] $\text{AM}(s'_r(\mathcal{K}\langle e' \rangle)) = \text{AM}(s'_r(e_1 e_2 \Delta (M, R))) = \text{map}^{s'_r(M)} \text{AM}(s'_r(e_1)) (\text{rep}^{s'_r(R)} \text{AM}(s'_r(e_2)))$. By proposition 7.3, there exists \hat{s}'_r such that $s_r \circ \hat{s}'_r$ satisfies $|C'|$ and by the construction in the proof, one such possibility is $\hat{s}'_r = [M \mapsto 1, R \mapsto 0]$. But then clearly $\text{size}(s_r \circ \hat{s}'_r, |C'|) = k + 1$ (because $\text{size}(s_r, |C|) = 1$ and the constraint sets only differ on the constraints introduced by the map removal), which requires that [3] $s'_r = s_r \circ \hat{s}'_r$ because s'_r is unambiguous at size $k + 1$ for $|C'|$. Hence, by [1] and [2], $\text{AM}(s_r(\mathcal{K}\langle e \rangle)) = \text{map } \text{AM}(s_r(e_1)) \text{AM}(s_r(e_2)) = \text{map}^{s'_r(M)} \text{AM}(s'_r(e_1)) (\text{rep}^{s'_r(R)} \text{AM}(s'_r(e_2))) = \text{AM}(s'_r(\mathcal{K}\langle e' \rangle))$.

Subcase REM-REP ($\text{rep } e \prec_{\text{rem}} (\lambda x. x) e \Delta (M, R)$):

By the definition of AM, we have [1] $\text{AM}(s_r(\mathcal{K}\langle e \rangle)) = \text{AM}(s_r(\text{rep } e)) = \text{rep } \text{AM}(s_r(e))$ and [2] $\text{AM}(s'_r(\mathcal{K}\langle e' \rangle)) = \text{AM}(s'_r((\lambda x. x) e \Delta (M, R))) = \text{map}^{s'_r(M)} \lambda x. x (\text{rep}^{s'_r(R)} \text{AM}(s'_r(e)))$. As with the REM-MAP case, we use the \hat{s}'_r construction of proposition 7.3 and the unambiguity of s'_r to argue that $s'_r = s_r \circ \hat{s}'_r$. Hence, by [1] and [2], $\text{AM}(s_r(\mathcal{K}\langle e \rangle)) = \text{rep } \text{AM}(s_r(e)) = \text{rep}^{s'_r(R)} \text{AM}((\lambda s'_r) s'_r(e)) = \text{rep}^{s'_r(R)} \text{AM}((\lambda s'_r) s'_r(e)) = \text{map}^{s'_r(M)} \lambda x. x (\text{rep}^{s'_r(R)} \text{AM}(s'_r(e))) = \text{AM}(s'_r(\mathcal{K}\langle e' \rangle))$.

Case $\mathcal{K} = \text{rep } \mathcal{K}'$:

By the definition of AM, we have [1] $\text{AM}(s_r(\text{rep } \mathcal{K}'\langle e \rangle)) = \text{rep } \text{AM}(s_r(\mathcal{K}'\langle e \rangle))$. Since $\text{rep } \mathcal{K}'\langle e \rangle \prec_{\text{rem}} \text{rep } \mathcal{K}'\langle e' \rangle$, [2] $\mathcal{K}'\langle e \rangle \prec_{\text{rem}} \mathcal{K}'\langle e' \rangle$ by the definition of the removal relation. Additionally, by inversion on C-REP, there exists τ and S_1 with $\sigma = [] S_1 \tau$ such that [3] $\Gamma \vdash \mathcal{K}'\langle e \rangle :_{S_1} \tau \parallel C$ and, similarly, there exists τ' and S'_1 with $\sigma' = [] S'_1 \tau'$ such that [4] $\Gamma \vdash \mathcal{K}'\langle e' \rangle :_{S'_1} \tau' \parallel C'$. Hence, applying the IH to [2], [3], and [4], we have that [5] $\text{AM}(s_r(\mathcal{K}'\langle e \rangle)) = \text{AM}(s'_r(\mathcal{K}'\langle e' \rangle))$. Combining [1] and [5] yields $\text{AM}(s_r(\mathcal{K}\langle e \rangle)) = \text{rep } \text{AM}(s_r(\mathcal{K}'\langle e \rangle)) = \text{rep } \text{AM}(s'_r(\mathcal{K}'\langle e' \rangle)) = \text{AM}(s'_r(\mathcal{K}\langle e' \rangle))$, as required.

The remaining cases are all similar to the $\mathcal{K} = \text{rep } \mathcal{K}'$ case and involve applying the IH appropriately. \square

References

Robert Schenck, Nikolaj Hey Hinnerskov, Troels Henriksen, Magnus Madsen, and Martin Elsman. 2024. AUTOMAP: Inferring Rank-Polymorphic Function Applications with Integer Linear Programming. *Proceedings of the ACM on Programming Languages* 8, OOPSLA2 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3689774>